

The Relationship between Parenting Pattern of Parents who Work Outside the Home to the Oral Hygiene of Preschool Children in Bobbin Area of Jember

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To examine the overview and relationship of parenting styles of working parents on the oral hygiene of preschool children in the Bobbin Area of Jember.

Metode: Parenting styles applied by each parent vary depending on their perspective. Various parenting styles applied by parents to their children include democratic or authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and uninvolved parenting styles. One form of parental concern for their child is maintaining oral hygiene. Preschool children are one of the most vulnerable groups to dental and oral health problems. This study is an analytical observational study with a cross-sectional approach and using purposive sampling technique. The study used 79 respondents who filled out a questionnaire.

Results: The average parenting style applied by parents is authoritative and the status of oral hygiene of preschool children is fair.

Conclusion: There is a difference in the value of the Oral Hygiene Index (OHI) of children in each application of parenting styles by parents, and there is a relationship between the parenting styles of working parents and the oral hygiene of preschool children in the Bobbin Area of Jember.

KEYWORDS: Parenting styles, Parents, Children, Oral hygiene, Oral Hygiene Index.

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INTRODUCTION

Parenting styles are a set of consistent behaviors applied to children over time¹. There are several types of parenting styles, namely authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and uninvolved. Authoritative parenting style is a style that can work together or be discussed with the child, authoritarian parenting style is a style that applies very strict rules to the child, permissive parenting style is a style that is less concerned with the child, and uninvolved parenting style is a style that neglects or hands off anything that happens within the child². The level of parenting style given to the child can be influenced by the type of job or career of the parent. Parents who work or have a career outside the home will result in minimal interaction time between parents and

their children, which will have an impact on reducing attention to the child³.

Parental attention towards their children can be demonstrated through the maintenance of their oral hygiene. Children of early age or preschool age typically lack the comprehension and capability to maintain their own oral hygiene and are dependent on their parents. Amongst this group, children aged 4 to 6 years old are considered the most susceptible to dental and oral health issues. This susceptibility is due to the fact that, during this developmental stage, children are still engaging in habits and behaviors that do not fully acknowledge the significance of dental and oral health^{4,5}.

The aim of this research is to investigate the depiction and correlation between the parenting styles of employed

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parents and the oral hygiene of preschool children residing in the Bobbin Jember region. In light of the aforementioned description, the investigator is inclined to explore the portrayal and correlation between the parenting styles of working parents and the oral hygiene of preschool children residing in the Bobbin Jember region.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The type of research conducted is analytical observational research with a cross-sectional approach and using purposive sampling techniques. This research was

conducted at five preschool educational facilities, namely Al-Mahrus II Playgroup, At-Taqwa Playgroup, Baitur Rahman Islamic Kindergarten, SPS Manggis 30, and Bhakti Mandala Kindergarten from September to November 2022, with a total of 79 respondents.

RESULTS

Description of Parenting Patterns of Preschool Children

Based on the parental parenting questionnaire filled out by the parents of the preschool children, the distribution of parental parenting can be seen in Table 1 as follows.

Table 1. Distribution of Research Samples Based on Types of Parenting Styles

No	Parenting Style	N	(%)
1	Uninvolved	0	0,00 %
2	Authoritarian	6	7,59 %
3	Permissive	11	13,93 %
4	Authoritative	62	78,48%
Total		79	100%

The data presented in Table 1 reveals that most preschool parents in the Bobbin Area of Jember practice authoritative parenting style, comprising of 62 parents (78.48%), followed by permissive parenting style with 11 parents (13.93%), while the third highest group is authoritarian parenting style with 6 parents (7.59%). It is noteworthy that no distribution of uninvolved or neglectful parenting style was found.

Description of average oral hygiene in preschool children

Based on the examination of oral hygiene using the Oral Hygiene Index (OHI) conducted on 79 preschool children in the Bobbin Area of Jember, the average OHI score data obtained can be seen in table 2 below.

Table 2. Mean Scores of Debris Index (DI), Calculus Index (CI), and Oral Hygiene Index (OHI) in Preschool Children in the Bobbin Area of Jember.

Oral Hygiene Index	Average DI Score	Avreage CI Score	Average OHI Score
OHI	2,25	1,56	3,38

Table 2 indicates that the mean score for DI, CI, and OHI are all in the fair category, suggesting that the average level of oral hygiene among preschool children in the Bobbin Area of Jember is fair.

Correlation between the parenting style of working parents and the oral hygiene of preschool children.

The correlation between the parenting style of working parents and the oral hygiene of preschool children can be determined by conducting a non-parametric test using the Spearman correlation (Spearman Rho). The correlation between the parenting style of working parents and the oral hygiene of preschool children can be seen in Table 3 as follows.

Table 3: Correlation between Parenting Style of Working Parents and Oral Hygiene of Preschool Children.

No.	Parenting Style	Average OHI Score	Sig.
1	Uninvolved	-	
2	Authoritarian	3,52	0,001
3	Permissive	7,12	
4	Authoritative	3,36	

The data in Table 3 reveals that parents with permissive parenting style have the highest average OHI score, which falls under the poor category, with an average

score of 7.12. Meanwhile, parents with authoritarian parenting style have an average OHI score of 3.52, falling under the fair category. On the other hand, parents with

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authoritative parenting style have the lowest average OHI score of 3.36, also falling under the fair category. No parents using uninvolved parenting style were recorded, therefore no OHI score average was calculated for this group. The table also presents the result of Spearman correlation test which indicates a significant relationship (sig <0.05) between the parenting style of working parents and the oral hygiene of preschool children in the Bobbin Area of Jember, as the null hypothesis (H0) is rejected.

DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows that the majority of working parents in the Bobbin Area of Jember apply an authoritative parenting style. This finding is consistent with previous studies conducted by Lestari (2018) at TK Al-Qodiri Jember and Roemin (2019) at TK Tiga Serangkai Meureubo Village, West Aceh Regency, which also reported that authoritative parenting style is commonly used by parents of preschool children, although some still use authoritarian and permissive parenting styles. The reason for this trend is that authoritative parenting style allows for freedom while maintaining parental supervision^{6,7}.

Table 2 shows that the OHI of preschool children in the Bobbin Area of Jember has an average DI score that falls in the fair category, with an average CI score of 1.56, also falling in the fair category. The average OHI score is 3.88, which is categorized as fair. This indicates that the oral hygiene of preschool children in the Bobbin Area of Jember is categorized as fair. This is consistent with the research conducted by Worang et al. (2014) on TK Tunas Bhakti children in the city of Manado, which showed that 27.2% of respondents had a good rating, 65.7% were rated as fair, and 7.1% were rated as poor. This is due to several factors that affect oral hygiene, including behavior, environment, healthcare services, and heredity. This is consistent with Blum's theory, which states that oral health status is influenced by environmental factors, behavior, healthcare services, and genetics^{8,9}.

Table 3 shows the results of data analysis, indicating that there is a correlation or relationship between parenting styles of working parents and preschool children's oral cavity hygiene with a significance value of sig <0.05, which is 0.001. This result indicates that the null hypothesis (H0) is rejected, meaning that there is a relationship between parenting styles of working parents and preschool children's oral cavity hygiene in the Bobbin Area of Jember.

CONCLUSION

1. The average oral hygiene status of preschool children under the application of authoritative parenting style falls in the fair category, similar to the average oral hygiene status of children under the application of authoritarian parenting style. Meanwhile, children under

the application of permissive parenting style have poor oral hygiene status. None of the parents adopt the uninvolved parenting style.

2. A relationship exists between the parenting styles of working parents and the oral hygiene status of preschool children in the Bobbin Jember community, as evidenced by a significant correlation coefficient in the Spearman correlation test with a significance level of 0.001 (sig <0.05).

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